

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Structural Bioinformatics Approach in Carcinogenesis

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ABSTRACT

Cancer continues to remain a prevailing disease, with no specific cures to it. The advancements in structural bioinformatics has benefitted different fields in modern biology, especially in biomedical practices for drug design. From the development in information technology, to the developing tools that screen for genetic expressions, structural bioinformatics can definitely provide more in the field of cancer, as it has done very little in the past two decades. The involvement of mutations and their comparisons to normal genes and proteins provides insight as to how the cancer develops, as well as the crystallization of these proteins help understand the cause of mutation. The article reviews to find out whether the application of structural bioinformatics practices can benefit cancer research, the tools used to do so and how it can aim to expand the subject.

Keywords: *Structural Bioinformatics; Cancer; Tumor; Protein*

INTRODUCTION

Biological research has seen many advancements over the years and it continues to be a growing dynamic field. One of the major developments in the field of modern biology is the advancement in the application of bioinformatics for medical practices. From computer programs and biological algorithms to pertinent databanks and impeccable softwares, bioinformatics has influenced and pushed the boundaries of modern biology (Chou, 2004). Predominantly, bioinformatics has provided a headway for protein sciences through structural bioinformatics, circumventing most of the

complications due to its dynamic principles (Gail J. Bartlett, 2003).

Figure 1. The regular procedure implemented in drug discovery. Structural bioinformatics was used in the later stages, but now benefits the earlier stages for homology recognition and identification (Tom L. Blundell, 2006).

Structural Bioinformatics is the specific study of analyzing and predicting the third dimensional structure of proteins, along with Deoxyribose nucleic acid (DNA) and Ribose nucleic acid (RNA). Structural bioinformatics' approaches in protein has been in creating renowned databases and portals, such as SWISS-PROT, GenProtEC and ExPASy that covers gene ontologies of organisms and their proteins produced (Gail J. Bartlett, 2003). Through structural bioinformatics, the protein information that can be obtained are its basic structure, the protein – ligand complexes, enzyme classifications and most importantly protein structure – function relations. In the field of biomedical researches, structural bioinformatics has pioneered in drug discovery and drug design. Designing drugs has become much easier due to the tools present due to technological advancements. Due to protein motif databanks such as PROSITE, developments in high-throughput crystallography and Nuclear Magnetic Resonance (NMR), designing and identifying drugs has become much easier and therefore, more bioinformatics methodologies have been implemented in the steps to analyzing drugs (Tom L. Blundell, 2006).

Even though there has been a major progress in technology and its biological applications, the use of structural bioinformatics still much more to offer in the

field of cancer studies. Structural bioinformatics, with all its abilities in gene predictions and protein interactions, has only scratched the surface for canceromics. Canceromics is a specialized study regarding cancer production, proliferation and metastasis and with the genes and gene interactions involved. In this article, we will discuss the implementation of structural bioinformatics and its use against cancer in general and more in specific to breast, colon and lung cancer as well.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

There are certain tools in the field of structural bioinformatics that are used for processes such as screening, analysis and predictions. Some of these materials are as follows:

1. Biomarkers

Biomarkers have been a key factor in the identification of cancer. Research has shown that in scenarios where certain screening procedures didn't show predicted outcomes, specialized biomarkers were implemented with accurate results (Jinong Li, 2002). The biomarkers also provide screening that can detect early-stages of cancers. Structural bioinformatics can play a large part in the identification of suitable biomarkers for cancer, where a combination of mass spectrometry, microarrays and protein – reading specific softwares, certain proteins can be analyzed for considerations as cancer biomarkers (Jinong Li, 2002).

2. Microarray

In the hopes of better understanding cancers, it is important to analyze the molecular levels of the cancer. As mentioned biomarkers

can represent the diagnosis on a molecular level, but in some cases, these biomarkers may not be of much help, due to the few number of tumor markers. However, by reading the genetic expressions of the cancer cells, a proper diagnosis can be determined. Regardless, microarray still has similar constrains to biomarkers, in that it would be less effective if the sample sizes were too small (Kim, 2004).

3. Protein Databanks

With the development in information technology, databases have started becoming more interactive and provide several different forms of data that have been collected through wet – laboratory methods. In today’s time, certain cancer related proteins have been crystallized and can be accessed through these databases, along with this sequence and other such information, ready to be analyzed. Crystallography has been a crucial part of protein biology and has now provided more leeway into cancer research as information regarding the function and three – dimensional structures of these protein crystals can be publically available within online databases.

Figure 2. Figure of TPEN tumor suppressor protein from the RCSB database (Crystal Structure of PTEN Tumor Suppressor, 1999)

Identification of mutation within normal genes is a very complex and meticulous

procedure. To sum it in a convenient fashion, it is as follows The step – by – step process of identifying cancer mutations from genes (figure 3).

Figure 3. The step – by – step process of identifying cancer mutations from genes (Shunsuke Kato, 2003).

The first step requires the understanding of the genetic sequence. From the sequences alone, we can identify the mutational differences. From then, we screen the two samples in a microarray setting, with different fluorescent markers present. Another use of the bioinformatics tool would be the data collection, where the data is produced by the microarray and collected. The data would mostly record the intensity of the mutations and replications, of the different genes within a gene region. These replications can be identified based on the fluorescence color, where in this case, red represents high intensity and green represents low intensity. Anything in between would be a dimmer shade of either color depending on the intensity level.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Crystallography also plays an important role since it can identify mutations, even when the result is cancer. The mutations in a region of the BRCA1 gene, identified as the BRCT region can mutate to disallow tumor suppression and therefore cause increasing growth of breast cancer (R. Scott Williams, 2001). These crucial mutations define the growth and proliferation of cancers, especially breast cancer, being one the most common types of cancer. Although Crystallography does not cure the mutation or act as a treatment, it provides insight in ways to better approach these mutating protein regions and better understand the mutations for further research.

Figure 4. A cluster view of the difference between p53 mutants and promoters and its intensities.

Furthermore, understanding the protein interactions between cancer – related proteins expresses the differences in regular proteins and the mutated ones (Gozde Kar, 2009). The function – mutation relationship of certain proteins can also be analyzed, where the p53 tumor suppressor protein was subject to mutation and then compared to identify the structure – function and function –mutation changes within the protein (Shunsuke Kato, 2003).

The result is shown as a form of a heatmap, where 2314 misense mutants of p53 plus p53. Each column represents a p53 mutant, where each row represents a p 53 promoter. The difference in between the mutation and the promoter is identified by fluorescence. These fluorescence intensifies from lowest (green) to highest (red).

Structural bioinformatics still has an interesting technique, which can pursue the outcome of cancer; reportedly breast cancer. Strcutural bioinformatics also deals with the dynamic state of proteins and therefore provides more insight as to where the mutation may occur, based on the current structure and more importantly the function of the protein (Ian W Taylor1, 2009).

Figure 5. The network of genes represent the cancer – related genes and how its intensity is related to prognosis patients.

Using the bioinformatics concepts of systems biology, it is possible to identify the certain genes in the progressive states, where each gene can represent the level of regulation in patients. Similar to the clusters, it is color coded based on the intensity of correlation in prognosis patients (Ian W Taylor1, 2009). This network also shows the relations between the cancer – related genes and how they may

influence one another considering the occurrence of mutation.

CONCLUSION

To conclude, there are a lot of benefits of understanding the structural and function impacts of proteins to identify diseases. Structural bioinformatics has provided several tools for the growth of protein sciences, drug design and drug discovery. However, even though by implementing all these tools for cancer research and treatments, there are only some benefits that can be provided by structural bioinformatics. With the implementation of structural bioinformatics, cancer research now has a better understanding of the genetic and protein – based information that can influence cancer growth. There are several techniques and tools, as mentioned, that can all benefit in accurately reading and identifying cancer growth. Biomarkers and microarrays are fine tools that can be used for analysis, whereas protein databanks can be used to better understand the functional errors that are caused during cancer growth.

However, there is a lack of research based on the practical use of structural bioinformatics, that can help prevent cancer and counter it before the later stages.

Therefore, more research must be done to implement bioinformatics techniques into cancer – based medical practices.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

We would like to thank Dr. rer. nat Arli Aditya Parikesit for providing us with the knowledge of structural bioinformatics and the opportunity for making this research article.

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